

The Mediating Effects of Grit on the Mental Health Literacy and Help-Seeking Behavior of College Students

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Abstract

In today's modern times and rapidly changing environment, the discussion of mental health and its rising significance is at its highest peak. The steady increase in mental health-related cases from various sectors showed the urgency of identifying new factors that contributed to such growing numbers. This was also true for college students, as they are a vulnerable population that is susceptible to mental health-related problems. This study introduces grit as a mediating variable that influences the relationship between mental health literacy and help-seeking behavior among college students. A quantitative, non-experimental, predictive-correlational research design with mediating effect analysis was used to examine the relationship among the variables. Using stratified random sampling, responses from 336 college students in Davao City, Philippines, were analyzed using descriptive statistics and mediation analysis. Based on the result, grit is a significant mediator between the mental health literacy and help-seeking behavior of college students ($p < 0.001$). This implies that cultivating the "gritty" personality of college students, together with their knowledge of mental health, can significantly increase their tendency to seek formal psychological services when experiencing personal distress and other related concerns to avoid future psychological problems, which might lead to elevated psychopathology. Further, the results expand the grit theory as a significant mediating variable in the field of mental health. The study recommends that college institutions and mental health practitioners to introduce the concept of grit in schools and to integrate it to existing mental health programs to enhance the services they provide for college students.

Keywords: *Grit, Mental Health Literacy, Help-Seeking Behavior, College Students, Mediating Analysis.*

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Introduction

Contemporary college students are in a state of rapid social change and face increasingly complex competition in today's modern society. Presently, with pressure coming from various aspects, psychological problems among college students are on the rise (Wissing, 2022). With the rising cases of mental health-related concerns among college students and the surprising decrease in the utilization of formal psychological services (Rickwood & Thomas, 2012), identifying new factors that can influence college students' help-seeking behavior is crucial to prevent mental health-related problems in their earliest stages.

There has been little literature investigating the attitudes and intentions of young people in the Philippines when it comes to seeking help for mental health concerns. One of the few research projects on such a topic surveyed 359 Filipino college students and found that only 22% sought formal psychological help for academic and non-academic concerns in their lifetime. These individuals preferred to seek help from friends and family members (Bello et al., 2013).

Furthermore, data from one private college institution in Davao City revealed that there has been a steady decrease in the utilization of formal psychological services even prior to the COVID-19 pandemic. Particularly, during the 1st semester of the school year 2019-2022, almost 300 college students sought counseling services. However, in the second semester of the same school year, such a number decreased by 48.7%. Moreover, during the pandemic, there was a further decrease of 48.8% in availing formal psychological services in the 1st semester of the school year 2020-2021 and another 20.3% in the 2nd semester of the same school year (Bangeles et al., 2024). Such a decrease had been continually observed even with the institution's promotion and frequent announcements of the services provided by the Guidance and Counseling Unit.

Grit – a relatively new phenomenon in the field of psychology – focuses on an individual's passion and perseverance for long-term goals (Duckworth et al., 2007). Individuals who are "gritty" are less prone to experience depression because they tend to focus on maintaining perseverance and passion to achieve their long-term goals instead of focusing on the negative facets of life. Most of the research conducted to examine grit among college students has been heavily focused on academic achievement and success, but not so much on mental health and psychological well-being (Datu et al., 2017).

This study aims to explore the mediating effect of grit on the college students' mental health literacy and help-seeking behavior.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to examine the mediating effects of grit on the mental health literacy and help-seeking behavior of college students. Specifically, this study aims to answer the following:

1. What is the sociodemographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 sex,
 - 1.2 age,
 - 1.3 year level,
 - 1.4 college, and

- 1.5 religion?
2. What is the level of mental health literacy among college students?
3. What is the level of help-seeking behavior of the college students in terms of:
 - 3.1 help-seeking intentions, and
 - 3.2 help-seeking attitudes?
4. What is the level of grit of the college students?
5. Is there a mediating effect of grit on the relationship between mental health literacy and help-seeking behavior among college students?

Hypothesis

The hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance

H₀1: Grit has no mediating effect on the relationship between mental health literacy and the help-seeking behavior of college students.

Theoretical Framework

The grit theory of Angela Duckworth (2007) explains that a "gritty" personality can maintain their stamina and interest in working towards their goals over time despite experiencing failures, setbacks, or plateaus in their progress. Duckworth et al. (2007) argued that high-performing individuals were not necessarily the most talented. Rather, these individuals were able to sustain their interests and efforts to achieve their goals despite failure, adversity, and discomfort. Grit reflects passion and effort sustained over time; thus, it can explain the completion of challenging goals despite obstacles and setbacks (Duckworth & Gross, 2014). Moreover, interest and effort are the two important components of grit because they contribute to continued persistence and dedication in completing and achieving specific long-term goals. A gritty person will approach an achievement as a marathon – his or her advantage is stamina. At the same time, boredom and disappointment will signal others to change the trajectory of their achievement and cut their losses (Duckworth et al., 2017). Datu et al. (2017) extended the theory to their concept of the triarchic model of grit, including adaptability to situations, which is an individual's ability to adjust effectively to life's ever-changing circumstances. It is characterized by expecting and accepting challenges, being flexible, and displaying a drive to overcome new difficulties.

The Theory of Planned Behavior by Icek Ajzen (1991) is commonly used in research, particularly for mental health help-seeking intentions and behaviors (Aldalaykeh et al., 2019; Mak & Davis, 2014; Zorrilla et al., 2019). The TPB was designed to explain and predict human behavior based on an individual's intention. Accordingly, one's behavioral intentions are influenced by attitudes about the behavior, the subjective norms towards the behavior, and the perceived behavioral control over achieving the behavior (Ajzen, 1991). Therefore, the stronger an individual's intentions towards engaging in a certain behavior, like seeking mental health help, the higher the individual's potential to perform the behavior or to seek mental health help. In theory, behavioral beliefs include the likely consequences of our behavior and produce a favorable or unfavorable attitude toward that behavior. Normative beliefs consist of the normative expectations of others, which result in the perceived social pressure or subjective norms of society. Lastly, control beliefs include the factors that may facilitate or hinder the performance of the behavior displayed. This gives rise to perceived behavioral control or self-efficacy.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Methodology

This study utilized a quantitative research design, particularly a non-experimental design with mediating effect analysis. Mediation analysis has been used to measure the causal process by which a preceding variable produces a mediating variable, which in turn causes a dependent variable, as well as the relationship between the two variables (MacKinnon & Valente, 2019).

Respondents

The respondents of this study were Filipino college students from 1st year to 4th year from one of the college institutions in Davao City, Philippines. Using stratified random sampling, 336 college students were identified upon which the data gathering was conducted. The strata that were included to determine the respondents were the seven colleges of the institution.

Instruments

This study utilized standardized questionnaires to measure the variables included. Specifically, the Mental Health Literacy Scale (MHLS) was used to measure the level of mental health literacy of the respondents. The Mental Health Literacy Scale (MHLS) is a 35-item univariate scale that is easily administered and scored. It measures six subscales, including Recognition of Disorders, Knowledge of Risk Factors and Causes, Self-Treatment Knowledge, Knowledge of Professional Help Available, Knowledge of How to Seek Mental Health Information, and Attitudes that Promote Recognition and Appropriate Help-Seeking. The MHLS displays good test-retest reliability and internal reliability as well. The first 15 items are scored on a 1-4 scale, with items 10, 12, and 15 being reversed-scored. Items 16-35 are scored on a 1-5 scale, with items 20-28 being reverse-scored. The total score is produced by summing all items (Max score=160; Min score=35) (O'Connor & Casey, 2015).

For the help-seeking behavior, the Mental Help-Seeking Attitude Scale (MHSAS) and the Mental Help-Seeking Intentions Scale (MHSIS) were used. The Mental Help-Seeking Intentions Scale (MHSIS) is a 3-item tool that is designed to assess respondents' intention to seek help from a mental health professional if they have a mental health concern. The MHSIS demonstrated evidence for high internal consistency ($\alpha = .94$; 95% CI [.929, .949]). Also, the MHSIS demonstrated strong evidence of predictive validity, with a correct classification rate of nearly 70% (Hammer et al., 2018). On the other hand, the Mental Help-Seeking Attitude Scale (MHSAS) is a 9-item instrument that was designed to measure a respondent's overall evaluation of their help-seeking attitude from a mental health professional if they found themselves dealing with any mental health concerns. Only a single MHSAS total score using the nine items should be calculated and interpreted. The MHSAS established its convergent validity and has demonstrated an internal consistency in both the exploratory ($\alpha = .93$) and confirmatory ($\alpha = .94$) subsamples (Hammer et al., 2018).

Finally, to measure the level of grit of college students, the triarchic model of grit scale (TMGS) was used. It is comprised of three areas, namely, consistency of interests, perseverance of effort, and adaptability to situations, and is measured using a 5-point Likert scale. Results of the study conducted by Datu et al. (2017) suggest that scores from the TMGS are psychometrically sound and provide a valid measure of grit in a collectivist society (i.e., the Philippines). Specifically, the reliability coefficients of the grit dimensions in the TNGS were: $\alpha_{perseverance} = 0.78$; $\alpha_{consistency} = 0.60$; $\alpha_{adaptability} = 0.88$.

Prior to the actual data gathering, the tools used in this study were pilot-tested on the same population for reliability testing and to ensure that the tools were appropriate for gathering the data. A minimum of 30 respondents from the study site were part of the pilot testing. Based on the analyzed data, the reliability coefficient for the Mental Health Literacy Scale (MHLS) using Cronbach's Alpha for inter-item consistency was found to be $\alpha = .883$. For the Mental Help-Seeking Intentions Scale (MHSIS), the reliability coefficient was $\alpha = .926$. Next, for the Mental Help-Seeking Attitude Scale (MHSAS), the reliability coefficient was $\alpha = .884$. Finally, for the Triarchic Model of Grit Scale (TMGS), the reliability was $\alpha = .773$. The overall reliability coefficient was $\alpha = .914$ using Cronbach's Alpha for inter-item consistency.

Ethical Considerations

In accordance with the ethical guidelines set by the Institution's Research Ethics Committee, this research underwent a proper evaluation and review to certify that the manuscript adheres to the institution's ethical guidelines and principles. Additionally, the Institution's Research Ethics Committee was active in monitoring the progress of this research. Consequently, respondents of this study were given an Informed Consent Form prior to the data gathering. The Informed Consent Form contains the nature, purpose, methods, demands, duration, risks, and potential benefits of the research before conducting the study. This was to ensure that their participation was voluntary and they could withdraw their participation at any time.

Furthermore, privacy and confidentiality of information were ensured throughout the data gathering. Code names were used for every respondent so as to hide their true identity, and all data were kept secure to ensure proper handling of their information. Finally, the research design used in this study emphasized fair treatment and selection to minimize biases and potential harm to the respondents.

Data Collection

The following were the procedures that the researcher followed in conducting the study, which included steps prior to, during, and after the data gathering. First, upon securing the Ethics Certificate and once the study was cleared, a request letter was given to the study site, specifically to the Office of the Vice President for Academic Affairs (OVPA), to conduct the data gathering at the said institution formally. Upon the institution's confirmation, the data gathering of this research had formally begun. The respondents were recruited via their Gmail accounts and were emailed the Informed Consent Form to ensure voluntary participation for this study. After agreeing to be part of this research, a Google Forms link was sent to their respective Gmail accounts, which contained the questionnaires included in this study. The Google Forms link included all the information and instructions needed to answer the questionnaires. Privacy and confidentiality of information were upheld throughout the data collection process.

Data Analysis

To analyze the gathered data, Descriptive statistics such as mean, frequency, and percentages were used to quantify the demographic profile, the level of mental health literacy, help-seeking behavior, and grit among the respondents. Next, a mediation analysis was used to determine whether grit has a mediating effect on the relationship between mental health literacy and help-seeking behavior of the college students. The analysis followed the Baron and Kenny (1986) approach and used bootstrapping with 5,000 samples to test the significance of the indirect effect.

Results

Table 1 shows the sociodemographic profile of the respondents. The respondents were from 1st year to 4th year under the seven colleges of the institution, with a total population of 9, 618 enrollees in the second semester of the A.Y. 2024-2025. First, the majority of the respondents were female (59.9%), followed by males (40.5%). Most of the respondents were from the first-year level (45.5%), followed by second-year level college students (37.5%), next were third-year level (12.8%), and finally, the fourth-year level (4.2%). In terms of age, most of the respondents were 19 years old (31.3%) at the time of the data gathering.

Further, in terms of their respective colleges, the School of Business and Management Education had the highest number of respondents in this study (34.8%), followed by the College of Humanities, Social Sciences, and Communication (14.9%), School of Teacher Education (12.5%), College of Hospitality and Tourism Management Education (12.2%), College of Engineering and Technology (11.0%), College of Criminal Justice Education (7.4%), and lastly, from the College of Maritime Education (7.1%). Finally, in terms of religious affiliation, the majority of the respondents were Roman Catholics (82.1%), followed by Muslims (6.0%), then Christians (4.8%), and Iglesia ni Cristo (1.5%). The remaining college students were part of other minority religions (5.7%).

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the College Students

Sex	f	%
Male	136	40.5
Female	200	59.5

Age		
18 years old	62	18.5
19 years old	105	31.3
20 years old	72	21.4
21 years old	44	13.1
22 years old	28	8.3
23 years old	11	3.3
24 years old	9	2.7
25 years old	5	1.5
Religion		
Roman Catholic	276	82.1
Islam	20	6.0
Christian	16	4.8
Iglesia ni Cristo	5	1.5
Other Christians	19	5.7
Total	336	100.0
Year Level	f	%
First Year	153	45.5
Second Year	126	37.5
Third Year	43	12.8
Fourth Year	14	4.2
College		
School of Business and Management Ed.	117	34.8
College of Humanities, Soc. Sci. & Comm.	50	14.9
School of Teacher Education	42	12.5
College of Hospitality & Tourism Mgt. Ed.	41	12.2
College of Engineering and Technology	37	11.0
College of Criminal Justice Education	25	7.4
College of Maritime Education	24	7.1
Total	336	100.0

Table 2 shows the level of mental health literacy of the college students. Based on the result, the respondents exhibited high levels of mental health literacy ($M = 113.34$; $SD = 13.03$). This means that their knowledge about mental health is sufficient, and the respondents are able to understand concepts related to mental health. Moreover, four of the six subscales have a description of high. This includes Recognition of Disorders ($M = 3.75$; $SD = 0.71$), Knowledge of Professional Help Available ($M = 3.41$; $SD = 0.57$), Knowledge of How to Seek Mental Health Information ($M = 3.73$; $SD = 0.84$), and Attitudes that Promote Recognition and Appropriate Help-Seeking ($M = 3.44$; $SD = 0.60$). This means that college students have sufficient knowledge on how to recognize disorders, knowledge about available professional help, and how to seek mental health information, as well as maintain an attitude to promote recognition of seeking appropriate help. Furthermore, the remaining subscales have a moderate description, including Knowledge of Risk Factors and Causes ($M = 3.11$; $SD = 0.64$) and Self-Treatment Knowledge ($M = 3.19$; $SD = 0.67$). This indicates that college students are knowledgeable but require additional exposure to concepts related to risk factors and causes of psychological problems, and knowledge about the danger of self-treatment.

Table 2. Level of Mental Health Literacy of College Students

	Mean	Description
1. Recognition of Disorders	3.75	High
2. Knowledge of Risk Factors and Causes	3.11	Moderate

3. Self-Treatment Knowledge	3.19	Moderate
4. Knowledge of Professional Help Available	3.41	High
5. Knowledge of How to Seek Mental Health Information	3.73	High
6. Attitudes that Promote Recognition and Appropriate Help-Seeking	3.44	High
Overall Rescaled Score	3.44	High
Total	113.34	High MH Literacy

Table 3 presents the level of help-seeking behavior of college students in terms of their intentions and attitudes to seek help. Based on the result, the overall intentions of the respondents to seek help when experiencing mental health-related concerns are high ($M = 5.37$; $SD = 1.48$). This indicates that the respondent's intentions to seek help are favorable and that they are willing to look for appropriate help. Moreover, the overall help-seeking attitudes of the respondents are high ($M = 5.74$; $SD = 1.28$). This indicates that college students' attitudes when seeking help in relation to their mental health concerns are favorable.

Table 3. Level of Help-Seeking Behavior of College Students

	Mean	Description
1. Help-seeking Intentions	5.37	High
2. Help-seeking Attitudes	5.74	High
Overall	5.55	High

In terms of the respondents' level of Grit, Table 4 shows that the overall level of grit is high ($M = 3.46$; $SD = 0.43$). This indicates that college students show significant passion and perseverance in maintaining their overall well-being. Moreover, two of the subscales have a high description, namely Perseverance of Effort ($M = 3.71$; $SD = 0.74$) and Adaptability to Situations ($M = 3.46$; $SD = 0.43$). This result suggests that college students are able to maintain their effort regardless if they face any form of adversaries and are flexible enough to overcome them. Finally, the subscale Consistency of Interest ($M = 2.51$; $SD = 0.85$) has a description of low. Such description aligns with previous studies revealing that Consistency of Interest has varying associations when paired with other factors, such as psychological well-being. Hence, the low description (Bowman et al., 2015; Rimfeld et al., 2016; Wolters & Hussain, 2015).

Table 4. Level of Grit of College Students

	Mean	Description
1. Perseverance of Effort	3.71	High
2. Consistency of Interest	2.51	Low
3. Adaptability to Situations	4.00	High
Overall	3.46	High

Finally, for Table 5, a mediation analysis was conducted to examine whether grit mediates the relationship between mental health literacy and help-seeking behavior among college students. The analysis followed the Baron and Kenny (1986) approach and used bootstrapping with 5,000 samples to test the significance of the indirect effect.

The *path a* coefficient, representing the effect of mental health literacy on grit, was significant, $B = 0.0079$, $SE = 0.0018$, $\beta = 0.2388$, $t(334) = 4.49$, $p < .001$, indicating that students with higher mental health literacy tend to have higher grit levels. The *path b* coefficient, representing the effect of grit on help-seeking behavior, was also significant, $B = 0.7223$, $SE = 0.1345$, $\beta = 0.2523$, $t(333) = 5.37$, $p < .001$, suggesting that higher grit is associated with greater help-seeking behavior.

The *total effect (path c)* of mental health literacy on help-seeking behavior was significant, $B = 0.0470$, $SE = 0.0045$, $\beta = 0.4973$, $t(334) = 10.48$, $p < .001$. The direct effect (*path c'*), after accounting for grit, remained significant but slightly smaller, $B = 0.0413$, $SE = 0.0044$, $\beta = 0.4371$, $t(333) = 9.31$, $p < .001$. The *indirect effect (path ab)*, representing the mediation effect through grit, was significant, $B = 0.0057$, $SE = 0.0018$, $\beta = 0.0602$, with the 95% confidence interval excluding zero (LLCI = 0.0027, ULCI = 0.0096), indicating that grit partially mediates the relationship between mental health literacy and help-seeking behavior.

Table 5. Mediating Effect of Grit on the Mental Health Literacy and Help-Seeking Behavior of College Students

Effect	B	SE(B)	β	t	P
a. Mental health literacy -> grit	0.0079	0.0018	0.2388	4.4935	0.000
b. Grit -> help-seeking behavior	0.7223	0.1345	0.2523	5.3708	0.000
c. (total) Mental health literacy -> help-seeking behavior	0.0413	0.0045	0.4973	10.4754	0.000
c'. (direct) Mental health literacy -> help-seeking behavior	0.0413	0.0044	0.4371	9.3056	0.000
ab. (indirect) Mental health literacy -> grit -> help-seeking behavior	0.0057	0.0018	0.0602	---	---

Figure 2. Mediation Model with Grit as a Mediating Variable in the Relationship between Mental Health Literacy and Help-Seeking Behavior of College Students

Discussion

This study examined whether grit has a mediating effect on the relationship between mental health literacy and the help-seeking behavior of college students. The result of this study has significant findings and interpretations.

First, based on the result, college students nowadays are more knowledgeable about the concept of mental health, specifically, on topics related to the recognition of disorders, knowledge of professional help available, knowledge on how to seek mental health information, and attitudes that promote recognition and appropriate help-seeking. This implies that college students in today's time manifest a certain level of understanding and awareness of common mental health concepts and have the knowledge to recognize behaviors that are detrimental to their mental well-being. According to previous studies, mental health literacy (MHL) helps to develop a positive attitude toward help-seeking behaviors. It helps promote the use of mental health services and reduces stigma and mental health illnesses (Jung et al., 2017; Jorm, 2012; Kim, 2020; Schnyder et al., 2017).

In addition, college students are familiar with when and how to seek professional help when experiencing personal distress and problems. This result is aligned with a previous study stating that being well-versed in the concept of mental health means students can make better and more timely informed decisions about their mental health and potentially help their peers (Owens, 2019).

Second, college students displayed high levels of help-seeking behavior through their intentions and attitudes towards seeking formal psychological services. This implies that when faced with personal and psychological stressors, college students are proactive in looking for available services that can help them deal with such problems. According to Fishbein and Ajzen (1977, as cited in Seyfi et al., 2013), positive attitudes can lead to a greater intention to perform certain behaviors. Hence, people with positive attitudes toward formal psychological help-seeking are more likely to seek help than those with negative attitudes toward formal psychological help-seeking (Kim & Park, 2009, as cited in Seyfi et al., 2013).

Moreover, the result of this study also confirms prior assumptions of the Theory of Planned Behavior by Icek Ajzen (1991). The theory was designed to explain and predict human behavior based on an individual's intention. Accordingly, one's behavioral intentions are influenced by attitudes about the behavior, the subjective norms towards the behavior, and the perceived behavioral control over achieving the behavior (Ajzen, 1991). Therefore, the stronger an individual's intentions towards engaging in a certain behavior, like seeking help for mental health concerns, the higher the individual's potential to perform the behavior or to seek help.

Third, in terms of the college students' level of grit, it was found that they have an overall high grit level. This reveals that college students tend to be passionate about achieving their overall well-being and are able to persevere and maintain consistency in their efforts to address any mental health-related concerns that come their way. Several research studies and evidence show that grit is associated with several indicators of well-being outcomes, such as life satisfaction, psychological well-being, and quality of life (Salles et al., 2014; Datu et al., 2016). Hence, the construct of grit could have protective effects against detrimental mental health outcomes. A gritty person is less likely to be prone to adverse mental health outcomes due to their tendency to experience failures and obstacles positively

Finally, using mediation analysis, it was found that grit as a mediating variable significantly mediates the relationship between mental health literacy and help-seeking behavior. Path *a* ($p = 0.000$), which indicates the effect of mental health literacy on grit, was found to be significant, suggesting that college students with higher mental health literacy tend to have higher levels of grit. Path *b* ($p = 0.000$) represents the effect

of grit on the help-seeking behavior of college students. The result was also significant, indicating that higher levels of grit are associated with greater help-seeking behavior. Path c ($p < 0.000$), which is the total effect, represents the effect of mental health literacy on help-seeking behavior and was found to be significant. Moreover, path c' ($p = 0.000$), which accounts for grit as a mediating variable, is also significant. In addition, path ab ($p = 0.000$), which is the indirect path, represents the mediation through grit, which was significant, indicating that grit partially mediates the relationship between mental health literacy and help-seeking behavior.

This result is greatly significant as it highlights that grit can be a mediating factor between the knowledge of college students about mental health and their behaviors toward seeking appropriate help. This indicates that a "gritty" personality, together with adequate knowledge about mental health, can lead to a favorable attitude and intention towards seeking formal psychological services. This is also in alignment with the prior study conducted by Özhan and Boyacı (2018), stating that improving grit within college students might be one way to improve the level of their anxiety, especially during their first year in college. Grit can be helpful in alleviating adverse mental health concerns and has been shown to have a negative correlation with both depression and anxiety scales.

The findings extend the grit theory beyond academic outcomes to a more inclusive discussion of mental health including one's help-seeking behavior. The grit theory by Angela Duckworth (2007) explains that a "gritty" personality can maintain their stamina and interest in working towards their goals over time despite experiencing failures, setbacks, or plateaus in their progress. Grit reflects passion and effort sustained over time; thus, it can explain the completion of challenging goals despite obstacles and setbacks (Duckworth & Gross, 2014). When combined with the Theory of Planned Behavior, the study illustrates that higher levels of grit reinforce one's behavioral intentions by sustaining motivation to seek help over time.

As a relatively new phenomenon in the field, grit has been constantly linked to academic success and the achievement of long-term goals. This study highlighted that grit is also a contributing factor in discussing mental health and its related concepts. In this context, college students with high levels of grit maintain their persistence and sustained effort when facing mental health concerns and display a drive to overcome certain difficulties. Therefore, college students who are knowledgeable about mental health tend to display determination and dedication to seek appropriate help when faced with challenges related to their mental well-being. They also maintain their interest and deliberate effort in receiving mental health support, regardless of whether there are setbacks in their attempts to look for appropriate psychological services available to them.

Conclusion

The findings of this research are integral in the field of psychological services as they highlight relevant factors that contribute to the help-seeking behavior of college students and emphasize grit – a relatively new phenomenon – as a mediating factor. This study highlighted that grit is a significant factor in mental health awareness and potentially contributes to college students' attitudes and intentions to seek help when faced with various psychological and personal stressors. Through the grit theory, it emphasized that college students who are persistent and able to sustain their interest and effort over time tend to actively seek ways to address certain challenges that come

their way, in this context, mental health-related concerns, despite challenges and obstacles that they may face. Therefore, improving the "gritty" personality of college students will help them navigate both academic pressure and personal concerns.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations and future directions as derived from the findings of this research: (1) improving the dissemination of mental health information as well as widening the sources of information of on-campus mental health services is essential to further enhance the presence of available psychological services for college students, (2) introduce and integrate the concept of grit through formal seminars or conferences and include a discussion on how to cultivate grit in relation to seeking appropriate psychological services when facing personal distress, (3) widen the scope of the research respondents from a single study site to multiple study sites to compare the mental health literacy and help-seeking behavior of the college students and to identify whether grit has a mediating factor across multiple sites, and (4) encourage future researchers to utilize the result of this study as a guide in developing research that will expound the grit theory and provide a new perspective in relation to mental health and help-seeking behavior.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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